

Supplementary Materials to: Walkability on street scale-level: An indicator-based assessment model

This repository contains data, code, and results of the work presented in the article ***Walkability on street scale-level: An indicator-based assessment model***. This document provides a structured overview of the supplementary materials.

1_Data

This folder includes all datasets used in the study to calculate the walkability index for the city of Salzburg.

- **OpenStreetMap Data:**
 - A complete dump from OpenStreetMap, which was used to calculate the road network graph and indicators.
 - Source: [Planet OSM](#), Date of Retrieval: November 11, 2021
 - Folder: *osm_20211119.zip*
- **Digital Elevation Data:**
 - Elevation data of Austria used to derive the indicator *gradient*.
 - Source: [data.gv.at](#), Date of Retrieval: March 31, 2019
 - Folder: *dgm_20190331_austria.zip*
- **Noise Polygons:**
 - 24h Noise exposure data for roads in polygon format used to derive the indicator *noise level*.
 - Source: [data.gv.at](#), Date of Retrieval: June 30, 2018
 - Folder: *umgebungslaerm_20180630.zip*
- **Image sampling:**
 - location of sampled images
 - File: *random_points_for_osm.gpkg*

2_Code

The code developed within the scope of this study was implemented to the open-source platform NetAScore© and is publicly available on GitHub. NetAScore provides a toolset and automated workflow for computing bikeability, walkability and related indicators from publicly available network data sets.

- Repository online: [NetAScore v0.9.0](#)
- Folder: *netascore-0.9.0.zip*

3_Images

- **Images of Random Locations in Salzburg:**

- Twelve images including textual descriptions used in the evaluation study.
- Folder: *images.zip*

4_Results

This folder includes outputs from the walkability assessment model and the survey results.

- **Enriched Road Network Graph:**
 - Contains computed walkability index values and corresponding indicators.
 - File: *walkability_osm_network_20211119.gpkg*
- **Responses of the online survey:**
 - Survey results downloaded from LimeSurvey.
 - File: *2022-05-18_survey-results.xlsx*